

Developing and managing solar farms to benefit soils

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Policy Context

Solar energy, especially in the form of ground-mounted solar farms, is playing an important role in decarbonising the UK electricity supply to meet Net Zero targets. However, consideration must be given to the impact solar farms may have on soils to maximise benefits and mitigate negative effects.

Our most recent analyses [\[link\]](#) are some of the first to demonstrate solar farm impacts on soils across a range of sites in England and Wales, offering important insights into how to manage solar farms for carbon storage and overall soil health.

Key research findings

Soils respond strongly to the presence of solar panels mounted on agricultural land in England and Wales. Understanding soil response to solar farms is important to inform design, construction, and land management options that provide long-term benefits for soils, including the delivery of important ecosystem services (e.g., soil carbon storage) and the provision of healthy soils to support biodiversity.

- Soil organic carbon was slightly higher (1.8%) in solar farms than in adjacent pastures when considering the entire solar farm (i.e., when accounting for the proportion of land under solar panels and in the gaps between solar arrays).
- Whilst the comparison between solar farms and adjacent pastures was based on only four sites, this finding demonstrates the potential to manage solar farms to promote soil carbon storage and sequestration at the site level to deliver dual benefits for climate and soils.
- Soil analyses from 32 solar farms revealed that soil carbon was lower under solar panels than in the gaps between solar arrays (i.e., the areas between rows of solar panels), likely due to reduced plant-derived carbon input to soils given lower plant cover and biomass recorded under solar panels.
- The difference in soil carbon between areas under solar panels and areas in the gaps between solar arrays highlights the importance of assessing soil carbon across the whole solar farm and account for the proportion of land under solar panels compared to areas not over-sailed by solar panels.
- Whilst these findings offer some initial insights, better understanding is needed of soil responses to solar farms by quantifying differences to adjacent land and collecting samples throughout a solar farm's lifecycle (i.e., before, during, and after solar farms operational lifespans).
- Given the diversity of soil types, plant communities, and land management practices across the UK, more research is urgently needed to elucidate solar farm impacts on soils nationwide, preferably by employing standardised protocols [\[link\]](#).

Policy recommendations

We call for public policymakers to identify appropriate opportunities, through formal policy mechanisms or otherwise, to embed soil considerations into the growing land-take for ground-mounted solar farms.

Specific policy [detailed [here](#)] and land management [detailed [here](#)] recommendations include:

- Developing best practice guidance that promotes the design, construction, and land management of solar farms to maximise benefits for soils and the delivery of ecosystem services. These may include:
 - Designing solar farms to deliver positive outcomes for soils (e.g., by increasing the proportion of areas free of solar panels).
 - Adopting construction practices that minimise impact on soils (e.g., by favouring the use of low-impact vehicles).
 - Managing the land to promote soil carbon sequestration (e.g., by seeding and maintaining plant species mixtures known to sequester carbon and improving grazing management).
- Formulating ecological and socio-economic indicators and metrics that are appropriate to underpin the development, implementation, and assessment of public policies that enable financial investment in soil carbon.
- Adopting a cross-sectoral and cross-government approach to form public policies aimed at realising Net Zero and improving soil health, particularly within the context of the low-carbon energy transition.
- Ensuring solar farms can access public financial incentives that encourage sustainable land use (e.g., the Environmental Land Management scheme).
- Implementing land use policies that incentivise funding from non-government sources (e.g., the private sector) into soil carbon markets and integrate financial data with systematic conservation planning approaches.
- Building equity and clarity into responsibilities and benefits for all actors involved when transitioning from agricultural land to solar farms.
- Regularly monitoring solar farms using standardised approaches [detailed [here](#)] to quantify impacts on soils and inform future policy and solar farm best management guidance [see example [here](#)].

Work with us

Dr Fabio Carvalho is a Senior Research Associate at Lancaster University and Prof Alona Armstrong is Professor of Energy & Environmental Sciences at Lancaster University, Director of Energy Lancaster, and Co-Director of the Sustainable Solar Energy Systems Network Plus. Their research focuses on the implications of the low-carbon energy transition for nature using a range of desk, field, laboratory, and modelling approaches and in partnership with the academic, private, public, and voluntary sectors.

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